

TYPES OF ACTIVITIES DEVELOPING THE CREATIVE QUALITIES OF THE FUTURE TEACHERS OF PRE-CONSCRIPTION MILITARY TRAINING

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Abstract. *Creative abilities are manifested first of all in independent choice, in discovering new things, in the ability to transfer knowledge to other situations, in solving original, non-standard problems. The modern era is characterized by the dynamics and complexity of social, scientific, technical and cultural development, the extraordinary difficulty of the problems facing humanity. This article describes in detail the pedagogical aspects of developing creative thinking and creative qualities of students of military education faculties.*

Keywords: *psychological, military education, creative, information technology, pedagogical, educational-ethical, scientific research, creative ability.*

The result of the reforms implemented in the education system of our country in the Republic of Uzbekistan is the "Concept of Higher Education Development until 2030", a new system of universal knowledge, skills, qualifications, as well as the experience of independent activity and personal responsibility of learners, or It is stated that they serve as modern core competencies.

Pedagogical and psychological research has the experience of researching pedagogical creativity in different directions. In the works of J.G.Yoldoshev, N.N. Azizkhodjaeva, O.Q. Tolipov, U.N. Nishonaliev, V.A. Slastenin, V.A. Kan-Kalik², pedagogical creativity in connection with the acceleration of the innovative process in education, psychological readiness to accept innovations in a systematic way it is highlighted, in the researches of A.V.Petrovsky, A.Maslov, pedagogical creativity is studied in connection with the ability of a person to be receptive to communication, the manifestation of communication culture.

In particular, according to G.N. Ibragimova, creativity is the basis of a person's creative activity. Also, creativity is a conscious, purposeful activity of a person aimed at knowing and changing existence, as a result of which new, unique, non-existent objects and other things are created aimed at improving the material and spiritual life of society. From this point of view, creativity is an independent type of activity that embodies all the positive qualities of human intelligence and acquires special activity related to the creation of new things. As mentioned above, he claims that the creativity of a person is evident not only in the fields of science and technology, culture, art and production, but also in the process of education.

Pedagogical-psychological resources have a strong socializing effect on the environment of future teachers. In general, the task of education should be to develop the creative qualities of students, which will help the student to reveal his creative abilities in pedagogical activities. The types of activities that develop the creative qualities of military education teachers until the next convocation have a certain influence on the stimulation of independent activity in the process of developing creative qualities it is important to create a positive environment, in particular, to form a group of future teachers as a circle of like-minded people.

Also, A.I. Avazboev, J.E. Pardaboev took a creative approach in organizing the professional activity of the future pedagogue with creative qualities, active in creating ideas that serve to develop the educational activities and personal qualities of new, advanced, future teachers. focuses on demonstrating, independent study of advanced pedagogical achievements and experiences, as well as having the experience of constant, consistent exchange of ideas with colleagues about pedagogical achievements. According to S. B. Jumanova, creativity in pedagogy is considered from the point of view of problematic situations and, in general, the ability to make decisions in countless tasks in constantly changing conditions.

The ability to make decisions in different situations also represents the following set of powers:

- the ability to express one's needs and interests;
- the ability to find other sources of information;
- the ability to make decisions in various pedagogical situations;
- the ability to create original ways to solve problems.

Creative thinking is thinking that leads to a new or improved solution to a problem. Critical thinking is testing proposed solutions to determine their feasibility. Creative thinking is aimed at creating new ideas, and critical thinking is aimed at identifying their shortcomings. Effective problem solving requires both creative and critical thinking.

In our opinion, the teacher's creativity in the process of pedagogical communication is manifested in several ways: creativity in the process of perfect knowledge of military education teachers until the next call; creativity in the system of mutual cooperation; creativity in organizing direct education; creativity in managing one's own behavior (conducting communication in a rhythm with self-awareness); creativity in the process of organizing mutual relations.

So, in the process of development, there is a motivational and value component expressed by the need for pedagogical direction, personal attitude to the acquisition and implementation of one's own knowledge, abilities, skills, as well as professional self-awareness. The existence of needs is a prerequisite for any activity, but the need itself is not yet able to give a clear direction to the activity. Motives include the effective meaningful nature of needs. The motivational value component implies interest in pedagogical and artistic activities (sustainable motives).

Also, J.P. Guilford connects creativity with the productivity of divergent thinking. In pedagogical sources, you can find his opinion that "creative-divergent thinking is a process." Initially, in addition to divergent thinking in the structure of creativity, the ability to change, the accuracy of the solution and other intellectual parameters were combined. He also proved that there is an inextricable connection between creativity and intelligence. He proposed to understand divergent thinking as a type of thinking that works in different directions, allows to change the methods of problem solving and leads to unexpected conclusions and results.

Based on the above points, we determined the following criteria of creativity: the ability to identify and create problems; the ability to improve the object by adding details; the ability to make non-standard decisions in various urgent situations; the ability to quickly solve problems; the ability to analyze and synthesize different situations.

So, personal creativity or personality formation is one of the most difficult problems of psychological-pedagogical study, which is primarily determined by the multi-level and subordinate structure of a creative person.

Thus, in Gestalt psychology, the following requirements were considered mandatory for the mental storehouse of creativity: not to be limited, not to be hidden by habits; do not simply and habitually repeat what you have been taught; no mechanical movement; not taking a partial position; do not focus on a limited part of the problem structure; acting not with partial operations, but with a free, open mind for new ideas, working with the situation, trying to find its internal correlation. According to A. Maslow, motivations, values and personal characteristics play a key role in determining creativity. The main characteristics of a creative person include cognitive ability, sensitivity to problems and independent thinking.

In the development of creative qualities of military education teachers until the next convocation, as mentioned above, it is important to create motives and conditions for them to demonstrate their knowledge, to feel the desire to really use the acquired knowledge in their professional activities. For this purpose, it is appropriate to use informative and cognitive materials aimed at the development of important personal qualities of future teachers, as well as the development of problematic elements of education, which help to organize students' research activities, identify different life and professions. and conflicts by them based on resolution. According to the methods of interaction between professors and future teachers, it is appropriate to use descriptive-illustrative, partially investigative, problem-based and research methods of teaching.

In particular, C. Taylor defines the following indicators of creativity: productivity of thinking, ability to plan activities, predictability of actions, decision-making and their implementation, ability to generalize. A. Maslow understands creativity as a condition that can be applied to any task in life. According to him, creativity is a quality inherent in every person from birth, but lost by many due to the influence of the environment.

In particular, the American psychologist E. Fromm proposed the following definition of the concept of creativity: "This is the ability to be surprised and learn, the ability to find solutions in non-standard situations, attention to discovering new things and the ability to deeply understand their experience."

H. E. Tryk creatively understands the past, the subsequent characteristics of the process, as a result of which a person (or a group of people) creates something that did not exist before. The criterion of creativity, in his opinion, is the characteristics and processes that activate mental productivity, in this regard, students should develop the ability to quickly respond to changes in the world around them, to think critically and think. He also points to the need to distinguish true creativity from fake and semi-creativity, which is a sign of innovation only due to non-conformity and lack of discipline based on blind rejection of what exists and the desire to be different. According to him, this kind of "innovation" has nothing to do with creativity. C.R. Rogers interprets the person-oriented approach to education and teaching as the main feature of pedagogical creativity.

Summarizing the definitions of creativity by scientists, we can conclude that there is no single approach to this problem, but the definitions presented to us can be classified according to four aspects that consider creativity: creative process, creative product, creative person and the creative environment (field, structure, social context that forms the requirements for the product of creativity). By joining the creative process, a person becomes active in a creative environment, acquires the characteristics of a creative personality, and as a result, develops creative qualities.

Most foreign scientists who consider creativity as a process (E.P. Torrance, X.E. Tryk S.A. Mednick) agree that creativity is divided into 3 actions: the action of promoting a hypothesis; act of creativity; the action of a logically developed idea.

According to the studies of Poincaré and Hadamard, the creative process is carried out in 4 stages: the preparatory stage includes an attempt to solve the problem in the usual way; the incubation period consists in realizing that the usual methods of solving the problem do not work, therefore, solving it is postponed, the person moves to another activity; perception is characterized by the sudden emergence of a response from the unconscious; verification includes a comprehensive analysis of the suitability and permissibility of the found solution.

From the scientific methodological recommendations noted in the research works of scientists G.N.Ibragimova, A.R.Aripdjanova, O.G.Pozdnyakov O.N.Ovsyannikova, J.P.Guilford²², E.P.Torrance, X.E.Tryk, S.A.Mednick combined with our ongoing research work: pedagogues should take a creative approach to the creation of educational programs and educational resources, and pay attention to the general development and professional formation of military education teachers until the next call; taking into account the ideologicalness, scientificity, visuality, systematicity of the prepared educational materials, consistent presentation of educational information, interdependence between educational information; assignments should be prepared according to the age characteristics of future teachers, their practical significance, specific goal orientation, and the needs and interests of military education teachers until the next call; purposeful, consistent use of methods, tools and technologies that develop creative qualities, as well as creative use of information technology opportunities in the organization of pedagogical activities; if the creative qualities of pre-service military education teachers are developed and a friendly environment is created by the teacher for active work of pre-service military education teachers in pairs and small groups, independent, creative, critical thinking skills and creative qualities develop.

Being teachers of military education until the next convocation requires high creative qualities from students, which is first of all manifested in independent choice, discovering new things, the ability to transfer knowledge to other situations, and solving original, non-standard problems.

The modern era is characterized by the dynamics and complexity of the development of social, scientific, and military techniques, and the extraordinary difficulty of the problems facing humanity. Until the next convocation, high professional training and discipline are not enough for teachers of military education, they require broad general knowledge and special knowledge, development of creative qualities through creative solution of technical and organizational and psychological problems. Based on the existing knowledge, future teachers are required to make the right decisions quickly in a changing environment and to predict their consequences in terms of time as mature specialists in the future.

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